

NOTES

(contd. table 1)

		(X = CH ₃)				(X = C ₂ H ₅)			
14.	H	213	YO	+	+	245	Y	+	+
15.	Acetyl	240	O	+	+	279	YO	+	+
16.	Phenyl	212	YN	+	-	214	BO	+	+
17.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	222	R	+	+	228	R	+	+
18.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	270	O	+	-	198	BR	+	+
19.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	210	YO	+	-	221	RO	+	-
20.	Guanidyl	285	Y	+	-	255	O	+	-
21.	α -Pyridyl	270	O	+	-	250	RO	+	-
22.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	270	Y	+	-	247	R	+	-
23.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	265	YR	+	-	240	R	+	-
24.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	142	YO	+	-	217	ON	++	+
25.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	270	Y	+	+	289	Y	+++	+
26.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	260	RN	-	+	253	OR	+	+

Yield = 71-78%

Yield = 70-74%

		(X = OCH ₃)				X = OC ₂ H ₅			
27.	H	235	O	+	-	220	Y	+	-
28.	Acetyl	234	YO	+	-	275	O	+	-
29.	Phenyl	218	OR	+	-	250	YO	+	-
30.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	215	O	+	-	240	RO	+	-
31.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	BR	+	-	270	BO	+	+
32.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	130	YN	+	-	275	ON	+	-
33.	Guanidyl	292	YO	+	-	259	YO	+	-
34.	α -Pyridyl	230	O	++	-	252	RN	+	+
35.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	268	RO	+	-	225	RY	+	-
36.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	258	RN	++	+	260	OR	+	-
37.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	204	YO	++	+	275	OR	++	+
38.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	262	SR	+++	+	284	Y	+++	+
39.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	235	OR	+	-	228	YO	+	+

Yield = 71-79%

Yield = 70-78%

		(X = C ₆ H ₅)			
40.	H	277	R	+	-
41.	Acetyl	270	OR	+	-
42.	Phenyl	236	R	+	-
43.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	245	YR	+	+
44.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	155	O	++	-
45.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	232	Y	+	+
46.	Guanidyl	250	SR	+	+
47.	α -Pyridyl	245	R'	+	-
48.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	270	OR	+	-
49.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	275	YO	++	-
50.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	172	O	+	-
51.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	220	RO	+++	-
52.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	250	Y	+	-

Yield = 70-78%

B = Bright, O = Orange, R = Red, S = Shining, Y = Yellow, N = Needles.
There was good agreement between C, H found and required.

References

1. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 985; 1976, 53, 163, 181, 827.
2. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, 37, 147.
3. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1975, 15, 176.
4. H. C. MUTREJA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, 16, 519.
5. H. C. MUTREJA, S. C. NIGAM, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 1056.
6. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Defence Sci., J. (India)*, 1975, 25, 55, 97.

Synthesis of a Thymol Derivative, 2-(2'-Isobutyryloxy-4-Methylphenyl)Propene from *Arnica amplexiculis*

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THE isolation of a thymol derivative, 2-(2'-isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl)propene (III) was reported from the root extract of *Arnica amplexiculis* along with other natural products¹.

The same product (III) has also been isolated from *Schkuhria multiflora*². We report here a short synthesis of the title compound.

2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone³ (I) prepared by Fries rearrangement of *m*-cresol acetate was treated with methyl magnesium iodide to yield 2-(2'-hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl)propan-2-ol (II). II on reaction with isobutyryl chloride and pyridine gave 2-(2'-isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl)propene (III). III was also obtained on treating II with isobutyric anhydride and potassium isobutyrate. The pmr spectral data of III was in complete agreement with that reported¹.

Dehydration of II with ethanol-hydrochloric acid yielded 2-(2'-hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl) propene (IV). IV was reportedly obtained from coumarin (V) by treatment with ethylene glycol and sodium hydroxide⁴. Treatment of IV with isobutyryl chloride and pyridine again yielded III. Methylation of IV was reported to yield the naturally occurring 2-(2'-methoxy-4'-methylphenyl) propene (VI)^{4,5}.

Experimental

2-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl) propan-2-ol (II): To a magnetically stirred suspension of dry magnesium turnings in dry ether (3.3 g, 25 ml), methyl iodide in ether (10 ml, 40 ml) was added slowly and refluxed slowly (1 h). The reaction mixture was then stirred at room temperature (30 min). To the resulting Grignard reagent (methyl magnesium iodide) was added 2-hydroxy-4-methyl acetophenone in dry ether (5 ml, 40 ml) and refluxed gently (1 h). It was then stirred at room temperature (1 h) and poured into a saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted twice with ether (50 ml). The combined ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The removal of solvent furnished 2-(2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl phenyl) propan-2-ol (II) (4.7 g) and was recrystallized from chloroform-petroleum ether, m.p. 66-67° (Found: C, 72.2; H, 8.4. C₁₀H₁₄O₂ requires C, 72.3; H, 8.4%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3500, 1615, 1585 cm⁻¹; δ (60MHz, CCl₄) 1.55 [6H, s, (CH₃)₂ C-OH], 2.2 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.92 (1H, bs, alcoholic -OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 6.43 (1H, br., d, J 8.5 Hz,

Ar-H *p*- to phenolic OH), 6.48 (1H, br., s, Ar-H *o*- to phenolic OH), 6.8 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H *m*- to phenolic OH), 8.85 (1H, bs, phenolic OH, exchangeable with D₂O).

2-(2'-Isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl)propene (III):

The phenolic alcohol II was dissolved in dry pyridine (1.6 g, 6 ml) and to it isobutyryl chloride (2 ml) was added. The resulting solution was refluxed (2 h). The contents were cooled to room temperature and poured into a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and crushed ice (8 ml, 25 g). It was extracted thrice with ether (40 ml), combined ether layer washed thrice with sodium hydroxide (5%, 30 ml) and finally thrice with water (30 ml) and dried over sodium sulphate. The removal of solvent gave crude product III (1.5 g). Chromatography on silica gel with petroleum ether-chloroform (4 : 1) as eluent furnished pure 2-(2'-isobutyryloxy-4'-methyl phenyl) propene (III) (1.23 g). (Found: C, 77.2; H, 8.1. C₁₄H₁₈O₃ requires C, 77.0; H, 8.3%); ν_{max} (neat) 1755 (phenolic ester), 895 cm⁻¹ (CH₂=CR₂); δ (60MHz, CCl₄), 1.23 [6H, d, J 7 Hz, -CH(CH₃)₂], 1.94 (3H, d, J 1.5 Hz, vinyl methyl), 2.27 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.6 [1H, septet, J 7 Hz, O-C-CH(CH₃)₂], 4.92 (1H, m, olefinic H), 5.02 (1H, m, olefinic H), 6.75 (1H, bs, ArH *o*- to ester), 6.90 (1H, br. d, J 8 Hz, ArH *p*- to ester), 7.21 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH *m*- to ester).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl) propene (IV):

The phenolic alcohol II (0.5 g) was dissolved in a mixture of ethanol and hydrochloric acid (3 ml, 2*N*, 0.5 ml), and heated under reflux (1 h). It was then cooled and poured into water (10 ml) and extracted thrice with ether (10 ml). The combined extract was washed twice with saturated sodium bicarbonate (15 ml) and finally thrice with water (10 ml). It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed to furnish crude IV (0.435 g). Chromatography on silica gel with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent gave pure IV (0.348 g). (Found: C, 80.9; H, 8.3. C₁₀H₁₂O requires C, 81.1; H, 8.1%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3430 (OH), 1632, 815 cm⁻¹.

2-(2'-Isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl) propene(III):

The styryl phenol IV (0.16 g) was dissolved in dry pyridine (1 ml) and to it added isobutyryl chloride (0.5 ml). It was refluxed (2 h), cooled to room temperature and poured into hydrochloric acid (50%, 3 ml) and extracted thrice with ether (10 ml). The combined ether extract was washed twice with sodium hydroxide (5%, 10 ml) and finally thrice with water (10 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent gave the crude ester III (0.155 g), purified by chromatography on silica gel G with petroleum ether-chloroform (2 : 1) as eluent. It was found identical with III obtained above by isobutyryl chloride pyridine method on II.

2-(2'-Isobutyryloxy-4'-methylphenyl)propene (III):

A mixture of phenolic alcohol II (0.5 g), isobutyric anhydride (3 ml) and potassium isobutyrate (0.3 g)

was heated (150-60°, 3 h), then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water (10 ml). The solution was kept at room temperature (12 h), diluted with water (30 ml) and extracted thrice with ether (20 ml). The combined ether extract was washed twice with saturated sodium bicarbonate (15 ml) and water (20 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of solvent furnished **III** (0.510 g), which was chromatographed on silica gel. The column was eluted with petroleum ether as eluent and the product obtained was identical with that obtained by isobutyryl chloride-pyridine method on **II**.

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References

1. F. BOHLMANN and C. ZDERO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1972, 2827.
2. F. BOHLMANN, J. JAKUPOVIC, H. ROBINSON and R. M. KING, *Phytochemistry*, 1980, 19, 881.
3. K. ONO and M. IMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1936, 11, 127; R. BALTZLY, W. S. IDE and A. P. PHILLIPS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2522.
4. K. J. DIVAKAR, B. D. KULKARNI and A. S. RAO, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 322.
5. G. WILLUHAN, *Planta Med.*, 1972, 22, 1 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 78, 20101).

Some New Thiosemicarbazones and 1,3,4-Thiazolinylnyls as Potential Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents

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THE tuberculostatic activity of thiosemicarbazones and related compounds was first observed by Domagk *et al*¹. Thiosemicarbazides and their derivatives possess various biological activities²⁻⁵ and are extensively used in medicine especially in the treatment of tuberculosis. Antimicrobial and antitumor activity are also shown by thiosemicarbazones^{6,7}.

Cyclization of thiosemicarbazides gives various heterocyclic systems depending on the reagent and other conditions of cyclization. 4-Substituted thiosemicarbazides on diazotisation gives thiazotriazoles⁸.

The structure of the reported compounds have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and infrared spectra. All the compounds have been synthesised according to the following scheme.

Synthesis and screening of 4,4'-di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (**I**) shows as tuberculostatic and antibacterial activity. 4,4'-Bis (5-arylimino-substituted benzaldehyde)-1,3,4-thiadiazolinylnyl-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl shows antibacterial activity.

Following bands are observed in ir spectra 1150 cm⁻¹ (>C=S), 1310 cm⁻¹ (>C=N) and 3450 cm⁻¹ (>NH). The band due to >C=N stretching is lost on thiadiazolinylnyl formation and strong tertiary amide stretch is observed around 1320cm⁻¹ and secondary amine shifts towards higher wave length at 3460 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

The ir spectra were recorded in Unicam SP-1025 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase.

4,4'-Di-(3-thiosemicarbazide)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl: To *o*-tolidine (0.01 mol) dissolved in ammonia (0.02 mol), carbon disulfide (0.02 mol) added and cooled below 30°. Ethanol (95%, 30 ml) was added and stirred for 30 min, contents allowed to stand for 2 h at room temperature. A solution of sodium chloroacetate (0.02 mol) was added followed by hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol, 50%), warmed and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to half its volume and allowed to stand overnight, when crystals of thiosemicarbazides separated, filtered washed with water, dried, recrystallised from ethanol (95%), yield 78%, m.p. 185°.

4,4'-Di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (I): 4,4'-Di-(3-thiosemicarbazide)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (95%, 50 ml) for 2 h, contents allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. and activity recorded in Table 1.

4,4'-Di-(5-arylimino-2-substituted benzaldehyde)-1,3,4-thiadiazolinylnyl-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (II): 4,4'-Di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (95%) and NaOH solution with a little water (5 ml). The mixture was heated on waterbath until